

Type-I seesaw extensions with superheavy dark matter: constraints from the Pierre Auger Observatory

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Superheavy dark matter?

- ☛ BSM physics at high scale?
 - SM instability scale: $\simeq 10^{10-12}$ GeV
 - Sterile neutrinos: $M_N \sim 10^{13}$ GeV in “vanilla” seesaw
 - Inflaton: $M_\phi \sim 10^{13}$ GeV
 - Grand Unification

- ☛ Superheavy particles including DM in type-I seesaw extensions?

- ✗ Issue: Fast decay $N_R \rightarrow h\nu$ from $y\bar{L}\tilde{H}N_R$ gauge-invariant operator
- ➡ Add an ultra-light SM singlet as a portal between SM and superheavy DM
- ➡ Add a superheavy SM singlet as DM itself

SHDM signatures in decay byproducts

- Expected number of (prompt) γ or ν from SHDM decay :

$$n_i(E, \mathbf{n}; M_X \tau_X) = \frac{\omega_i(E, \mathbf{n})}{4\pi M_X \tau_X} \frac{dN_i}{dE} \int_0^\infty ds \rho_{\text{DM}}(\mathbf{x}_\odot + s\mathbf{n})$$

Super-heavy
particles

large fluxes of
photons and
neutrinos

- $\omega_i(E, \mathbf{n})$: directional exposure to species i
- Integration of DM profile $\rho_{\text{DM}}(\mathbf{x})$ along line of sight
- dN_i/dE : energy spectrum of species i subsequent to the decay of X , determined by decay channels and fragmentation functions
- M_X and τ_X : parameters governed by specific models

Air shower observables (hybrid observation)

Detection of UHE gamma rays

Search for deep and muon-poor showers

Horizon limited to a few Mpc, ideal smoking gun for SHDM

Detection of UHE neutrinos

- Search for quasi-horizontal showers with electromagnetic counterpart
- See talk by S. Sehgal at this conference

- Gpc horizon, ideal smoking gun for BSM physics, including SHDM

Benchmark constraints

- Best constraints on τ_X from sensitivity to UHE γ s for $M_X \gtrsim 10^9$ GeV

☛ $\tau_X > 10^{30}$ s viable?

- Pseudo-scalar X interacting with sterile-neutrinos sector:

(motivated by several UV models with string or higher-dimensional inspired moduli fields)

- Extended Seesaw framework:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{\nu}_L & \bar{\chi}_R^c & \bar{N}_R^c \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \delta m & m_D \\ \delta m & m_\chi & 0 \\ m_D & 0 & M_N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_R^c \\ \chi_R \\ N_R \end{pmatrix}$$

with $\delta m \ll m_\chi \ll m_D \ll M_N$

- Mass eigenstates controlled by mixing angle $\theta_m = \delta m / m_\nu \ll 1$:

$$\nu_1 \simeq (\chi_R + \chi_R^c) + \theta_m (\nu_L + \nu_L^c)$$

$$\nu_2 \simeq (\nu_L + \nu_L^c) - \theta_m (\chi_R + \chi_R^c)$$

$$\nu_3 \simeq N_R$$

☛ $X \rightarrow h\nu_1\nu_2$ decay channel:

☛ Decay width controlled by $(m_2/v)^2$ and θ_m^2 :

$$\Gamma_{h\nu_1\nu_2}^X = \frac{\alpha_X^2 \theta_m^2}{192\pi^3} \left(\frac{M_X}{M_P}\right)^2 \left(\frac{m_2}{v}\right)^2 M_X$$

Metastability through sterile-neutrino portal

- End-to-end calculation of expected number of UHE gamma rays/neutrinos
- [Pierre Auger Collab., Phys. Rev. D 109 (2024) L081101]

- Extended Seesaw framework:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \overline{\nu}_L & \overline{\chi}_R^c & \overline{N}_R^c \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \delta m & m_D \\ \delta m & M_\chi & \delta M \\ m_D & \delta M & M_N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_R^c \\ \chi_R \\ N_R \end{pmatrix}$$

with $\delta m \ll \delta M \ll m_D \ll M_\chi < M_N$

- Mass eigenstates controlled by $\theta_N = \delta m/M_N$ and $\theta_\chi = \delta M/(M_N - M_\chi)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\nu} &\simeq (\nu_L + \nu_L^c) + \theta_N(N_R + N_R^c), \\ \tilde{\chi} &\simeq (\chi_R + \chi_R^c) - \theta_\chi(N_R + N_R^c), \\ \tilde{N} &\simeq (N_R + N_R^c) + \theta_N(\nu_L + \nu_L^c) + \theta_\chi(\chi_R + \chi_R^c), \end{aligned}$$

- $\tilde{\chi} \rightarrow h\tilde{\nu}$ decay channel:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{y_N}{\sqrt{2}} h \left(\overline{\nu}_L N_R + \overline{N}_R \nu_L \right) &= \dots + \frac{i y_N \theta_\chi}{2\sqrt{2}} h \left(\overline{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\chi} + \overline{\tilde{\chi}} \tilde{\nu} \right) + \dots \\ \Gamma_{\tilde{\chi} \rightarrow h\tilde{\nu}} &= \frac{|y_N|^2 \theta_\chi^2}{256\pi} M_{\tilde{\chi}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

- End-to-end calculation of expected number of UHE nucleons, gamma rays and neutrinos
- Secondary UHE gamma rays from ICS negligible
- Secondary UHE gamma rays from synchrotron important only for $M_X \gtrsim 10^{13}$ GeV

Justification of the mass hierarchies?

- ➔ High-scale U(1) global symmetry, with sector of superheavy Weyl $\{\psi, \tilde{\psi}\}$ fermions with mass M_P and scalars with vevs $\sim 10^{12-13}$ GeV

X	L	χ_R	N_R	ϕ_χ	ϕ_N	ψ_1	$\tilde{\psi}_1$	ψ_2	$\tilde{\psi}_2$	ψ_3	$\tilde{\psi}_3$	ψ_4	$\tilde{\psi}_4$
0	-1	+5	+1	-	-2	-3	+3	-1	+1	+1	-1	+3	-3
-	-1	-7	+1	+14	-2	+1	-1	-13	+13	-11	+11	-9	+9

- ➔ After spontaneous symmetry breaking, seesaw framework as a low-energy effective theory with:

$$\bullet m_\chi = \frac{2\lambda_{S4}\lambda_{43}\lambda_{32}\lambda_{21}\lambda_{15}\langle\phi_N\rangle^5}{M_P^4}$$

$$\bullet M_N = 2\lambda_N\langle\phi_N\rangle$$

$$\bullet \theta_m = \frac{\lambda_{3L}\lambda_{43}\lambda_{S4V}\langle\phi_N\rangle^2}{m_\nu M_P^2}$$

$$\bullet M_\chi = 2\lambda_\chi\langle\phi_\chi\rangle$$

$$\bullet M_N = 2\lambda_N\langle\phi_N\rangle$$

$$\bullet \delta M = \frac{\lambda_{1N}\lambda_{12\chi}\lambda_{23N}\lambda_{34N}\lambda_{4\chi}\langle\phi_N\rangle^4\langle\phi_\chi\rangle}{M_P^4}$$

- ➔ Benchmark target:

$$\theta_m \sim 10^{-6} \text{ for } M_\chi = 10^9 \text{ GeV}$$

- ➔ Benchmark target:

$$\delta M \sim 10^{-18} \text{ for } M_\chi = 10^{10} \text{ GeV}$$

Conclusions

- Continuous searches of UHE gamma rays and neutrinos at the Pierre Auger Observatory
- Upper limits on fluxes of considerable interest for UHECR astrophysics *and* BSM physics
- Particular BSM case: SHDM
- Best constraints on τ_χ from Auger gamma-ray limits (in general) for $M_\chi \gtrsim 10^9$ GeV
- Type-I seesaw extensions still viable to explain SHDM